

Media entrepreneurship

By: Abel Suing abelsuing@gmail.com

In Ecuador, the organic laws on Intercultural Education and Entrepreneurship and Innovation encourage the creation of new productive units to serve the communities. The aim is to design goods and services, promote an entrepreneurial culture and coordinate with other actors to improve social and economic development.

Current secondary and higher education curricula in the country include content on entrepreneurship. In addition, there are programmes, fairs and events run by local governments aimed at overcoming limitations in the conception and practice of innovations, but there is still a long way to go to adapt to changes in international markets and the diversification of online commerce.

It would seem that small cities, such as Loja, are not affected by tariff policies or regulations on digital platforms, but this is not the case. In recent decades, imports from China have multiplied. In social networks, consumption models that minimise local producers and increase luxury purchases are exalted.

And although it may not be evident to all citizens, society is moving towards clean energies, that is, it is extremely urgent to change the extractivist economy towards other alternatives. And it is here where the media can contribute through informative pedagogy, and together with educational institutions, increase the visibility of new ideas that lead to the creation of companies, generate jobs and well-being.

There is an urgent need to overcome risk aversion and the history of Spanish colonialism in Latin America. There is still an administrative and paternalistic vision that leads to dependence on the state. Even today many young people go to university to qualify as the next civil servants, few aspire to set up their own company.